

COMMERCIAL BANKS INNOVATIVE PRODUCTS AND LOYALTY PROGRAMS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Technological development, online platforms and remote services are directly related to innovations in the financial industry. All above mentioned in turn increases quantitative and qualitative operational risks and the likelihood of bankruptcy. Despite the risks, banks are constantly trying to offer customers innovative products and services. Based on the experience of foreign countries, they use electronic technology services. Loyalty programs increase customer satisfaction and bank income. Premium services and privileged position are especially important for business people who have a solid financial situation and do not have enough time to manage personal matters. Customers using premium services are characterized by loyalty, trust and long-term relationships with the serving bank. The goal of loyalty programs in the short term is to increase the bank's awareness among the population, and in the long term to attract new customers and retain existing customers. True loyalty on the part of the customer means that the customer remains loyal to the bank serving them despite the better offer by a competing bank. Customer loyalty is influenced by: age, geographical location, gender, nationality, income, etc.

Keywords: National Bank of Georgia, Net Profit, Customers, Digital Technologies, Points Accumulation Program.

INTRODUCTION

In Georgia the activities of commercial banks are regulated by the Central Bank of Georgia, that was established in 1919 under the name “State Bank of Georgia” and began operating in 1920. Its original function was to ensure the circulation of money, the stability of monetary signs and the issuance of loans for the development of agriculture.

Banking in Georgia is regulated by the National Bank of Georgia, which has been independent since 1991 and carries out both the supervision of commercial banks and the provision and maintenance of the stability of the banking system. The National Bank of Georgia is independent in its activities and representatives of the legislative and executive authorities do not have the right to interfere in its activities.

The independence of the National Bank is regulated by the existing law: “On the National Bank of Georgia”, which defines its functions, rules of activity, rights and obligations. The National Bank is responsible for producing and disseminating statistics on the country's financial and external sectors in accordance with international standards and methodologies.

The National Bank is also responsible for the payment system in the country and its proper functioning. It issues currency - money, and also ensures the minting of coins for circulation or numismatic purposes. The National Bank supervises the Law "On Financing the Prevention of

Money Laundering and the Financing of Terrorism". This supervision is carried out in accordance with a risk-based approach and is controlled both remotely and through on-site inspections.

Commercial banks are regulated by: 1. The Organic Law of Georgia "On the National Bank of Georgia"; 2. The Law of Georgia "On the Activities of Commercial Banks"; 3. Other legal acts.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research makes it possible to use a mixed-methods approach. The research design incorporates both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. To improve the validity of the research findings and triangulate the information, there are used surveys, interviews and case studies, as well as secondary data analysis.

In connection with the study, in order to find legal concepts, in the research is used the juridical-normative approach method: The law "On the National Bank of Georgia"; The law "On Financing the Prevention of Money Laundering and the Financing of Terrorism"; The Organic Law of Georgia "On the National Bank of Georgia"; The Law of Georgia "On the Activities of Commercial Banks"; Other legal acts.

Main part

As of 2024, there are 17 commercial banks in Georgia. They classify customers according to their income and provide highly qualified service. Banks try to adapt their products to their customers as much as possible and thus attract potential customers. Banks allocate significant resources and expenses to create loyalty programs in order to become more reliable and caring for customers.

According to the financial reports of operating commercial banks, as of January-July 2024, the National Bank of Georgia reported that 1.81 billion GEL net profit was generated. In this regard, the Bank of Georgia is leading with a profit of 921 million GEL, TBC Bank is in second place with 683 million GEL, and Liberty Bank is in third place with 66 million GEL.

Among the five commercial banks with losses are VTB Bank - 9.3 million GEL, Silk Bank, Hash Bank, Paysera Bank Georgia and Pave Bank.

No	Name of The Bank	Market Share			
		Total Assets	NET Interest Income	Net Fee and Commission Income	NET Income
1	Bank of Georgia	39.09%	41.06%	49.99%	49.03%
2	TBC Bank	38.83%	32.78%	37.26%	38.54%
3	Liberty Bank	5.26%	7.55%	3.81%	3.74%
4	Basis Bank	4.14%	3.74%	1.10%	2.43%
5	Credo Bank	3.24%	6.83%	5.35%	1.92%
6	ProCredit Bank	2.15%	1.74%	0.01%	1.11%
7	Tera bank	2.11%	1.76%	0.72%	0.97%
8	Cartu Bank	1.94%	1.72%	0.75%	1.32%
9	HALYK Bank	1.03%	0.95%	0.16%	0.63%

10	Pasha Bank	0.66%	0.64%	0.20%	0.28%
11	VTB Bank Georgia	0.51%	0.17%	0.00%	-0.17%
12	IS Bank	0.46%	0.55%	0.45%	0.52%
13	Ziraat Bank	0.26%	0.34%	0.22%	0.20%
14	Silk Bank	0.25%	0.14%	0.00%	-0.35%
15	Paysera Bank Georgia	0.03%	0.01%	0.01%	-0.05%
16	Hash Bank	0.01%	0.02%	-0.01%	-0.13%
17	Pave Bank	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	-0.01%
	Total Banking Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Source: <https://nbg.gov.ge/en/supervision/banking-supervision>

During the Soviet period, there were no independent banks in Georgia for 70 years. The banking system in Georgia dates back to 1991, when the first commercial banks were established. The ease of registration and obtaining a license contributed to the opening of hundreds of banks, however, due to the misappropriation of deposits from the population, they soon ceased to function. After these facts, public confidence in banks weakened, which was compounded by the failure of state savings banks to return savings from the population. However, it is noteworthy that TBC Bank and Bank of Georgia, that appeared on the Georgian market in the 1990s, have successfully managed to continue and develop their activities to this day.

Despite the decrease in the number of commercial banks in recent decades, the banking sector in the country has grown, which, together with the development of the country's economy, has led to an increase in the number of employees in the sector.

The improvement of service from commercial banks was facilitated by the development of remote services, which became even more active during the Covid pandemic. The banking sector quickly adapted and as a result, banks retained both customers and income.

Georgia's banking sector is among the top ten in the world in terms of profitability.

The development of digital technologies has led to the development of Internet banking, information and contact chats on websites, mobile banking applications, etc. Nowadays, business and innovation are inextricably linked. Financial institutions that use digital technologies are more attractive to customers, as they offer more effective financial services. Innovations implemented in banks simplify the use of banking products, make them more accessible and comfortable, all that in turn increases customer loyalty to a particular commercial bank.

Part of the Georgian population has difficulty of accepting innovations and news, despite this, commercial banks, in compliance with international standards, offer customers innovative services and the ability to perform simple operations without visiting the bank using the nearest devices: ATM, PAY BOX, Digipass.

Innovative products and technologies make it possible to use bank services during non-working hours and days, from any geographical location.

Recently, commercial banks have launched several financial products, including: Fintech.ge, SPACE, WallyPay. They are completely digitalized and represent virtual accounts.

Remote service and self-service save time and money for the bank and the customer, and reduce the number of bank employees. Since 2020, through digital wallets, customers no longer even have to use cards, which further reduces physical contact.

One of the innovative products created during the pandemic is the use of mobile banking without mobile Internet. The innovative product of JSC “Bank of Georgia” - an adapted ATM for the blind provides information to blind customers with a voice program and helps them complete transactions completely independently.

An innovative product is also a smart POS terminal with the function of a cash register.

The most popular and widely used innovative product of JSC “Bank of Georgia” recently is Apple Pay, and for Android users, the TSKAPP application, which allows you to perform exactly the same operations as Apple Pay, with the only difference being that it makes payments only at the POS terminal.

Among the innovative products is a digital card. It can be purchased/activated via internet banking and mobile banking, and is functionally the same as a plastic card. Its advantage is that this card does not physically exist, it is impossible to lose it, forget it or have someone else use the card data.

Since 2020, JSC “Bank of Georgia” has been offering its customers a globally innovative product: payment with a smile, i.e. travel without using a travel card. FACE RECOGNITION is a product that has no analogues in the Georgian market and has also been introduced in CAMEA (Central Europe, Middle East and Africa) countries. The user fixes his face with the turnstile camera and passes through it in the subway without a card.

An innovation in individual banking services is the bank advisor, with the help of whom banking issues are resolved and consulted remotely, via telephone communication, which saves time for the user.

The disadvantages of innovative technologies are: 1. As a result of remote service, the user has lost contact with the bank; 2. According to some users, operations carried out through the Internet bank are unreliable and contain a high level of risk.

Innovations in the financial industry are mainly related to remote services, online platforms and technological development, which in turn increases quantitative and qualitative operational risks and the likelihood of bankruptcy. However, despite the risks, banks are constantly trying to offer customers innovative products and services. Based on the experience of foreign countries, they use electronic technology services. Loyalty programs increase customer satisfaction and bank income.

Customers have difficulty adapting to innovations, have a “fear” only when interacting with technology, so they prefer to visit a branch. Despite this, banks are constantly introducing modern technologies, do not spare efforts and resources on digitalization and training internal

talents. The development of the banking sector depends on innovations and is vital for its functioning.

Privileged, premium services are especially important for business people who have a solid financial situation and do not have enough time to manage personal matters. Customers using premium services are characterized by loyalty, trust and long-term relationships with the serving bank.

Commercial Bank Loyalty Programs

The loyalty program dates back to the late 18th century. According to an article in the New York Times, in 1793, a retailer in Sudbury gave his customers copper coins that allowed them to buy products. This method of loyalty program was used in the market for a long time, but due to the high cost of printing copper coins, at the end of the nineteenth century, retailers began to use a new method of loyalty program, the so-called Green Shield stamps.

In the modern international banking system, the most common form of loyalty programs is the accumulation of points and the so-called cashback. One of the largest British banks, Barclays, prefers the cashback program and returns different amounts to customers for using different types of banking products in exchange for paying a commission. For example, 3 pounds for using insurance products, and 5 pounds for a mortgage loan.

The German Deutsche Bank operates a points accumulation program and awards customers express points for everyday transactions, each customer has the opportunity to accumulate more than 1250 points per month. The accumulated points can be spent within 12 months.

Commercial banks use loyalty programs to attract customers and build long-term relationships with them. These programs are beneficial for both the bank and the customer. Loyalty programs are associated with costs and are mainly determined by long-term results, although companies still agree to implement them.

There are three types of bank loyalty programs in the world:

- 1) Accumulation cards: accumulation of points and bonuses;
- 2) Special offers for special and important customers;
- 3) Recognition programs: giving gifts to customers, congratulating them on holidays, etc.

The goal of loyalty programs in the short term is to increase the bank's awareness among the population, and in the long term to attract new customers and retain existing customers.

The benefits of loyalty programs are:

1. Maintaining customer loyalty.
2. Customer satisfaction with the loyalty program.
3. The customer's desire to join the desired loyalty program.

True loyalty on the part of the customer means that the customer remains loyal to the bank serving them despite the better offer by a competing bank.

Customer loyalty is influenced by: age, geographical location, gender, nationality, income, etc.

An indicator of the success of a loyalty program is:

1. The number of members involved in the program who are desirable for the program and the bank. To achieve this, companies even create barriers to membership, for example: a. After filling out an application on the website, it is possible to receive a card only a few weeks later; b. At the first stage, a temporary card is issued to the user and only after an application is filled out to receive a main card. It is also worth noting that the activity of members is determined by the range of gifts received.
2. The activity of members involved in the program - the speed of accumulating bonuses and the ability to receive a gift soon increases satisfaction even more. Therefore, to accelerate the accumulation of bonuses, companies provide the opportunity to accumulate points in several organizations with one card.
3. Program profitability - how much money the organization has to invest, the correct segmentation of program members and effective communication with them.

A loyal, committed and financially profitable customer is important for the bank. A loyal customer avoids products offered by a competing bank. The benefits offered by the loyalty program provide an incentive for customers to purchase the bank's product and become dependent on this company.

Loyalty Program- The Case of JSC “Bank of Georgia”

The goal of commercial banks is to attract customers, gain and maintain trust, gain their loyalty and thereby receive more benefits.

In conditions of increasing competition between companies in Georgia, loyal customers are especially important for sellers of frequently consumed products: supermarkets, pharmacies, banks, etc. Research confirms that 84% of consumers prefer brands that offer a loyalty program, and for 66% of consumers, the opportunity to receive bonuses actually changes their spending behavior.

For example, JSC “Bank of Georgia” offers its customers a large-scale loyalty program - PLUS, which combines health and property insurance, the function of accumulating points on the card and discounts on banking products. The Plus program includes three statuses: PLUS CLASSIC, PLUS SILVER and PLUS GOLD. There are different ways to accumulate points on the card:

1. During payments at POS terminals;
2. When making online payments;
3. At payment machines;
4. When paying in mobile/internet banking;
5. Plus points are also accumulated based on the recommendation of other users.

This loyalty program is distinguished by innovations, offering discounts at retail outlets. Plus points can be used or exchanged for purchasing various services and products through mobile/internet banking. On the online platform, it is possible to browse the catalog, view offers and use points.

When discussing loyalty programs in the financial sector, the American Express credit card is worth mentioning with its diverse loyalty program. The Amex cardholder can take advantage of global offers anywhere in the world, and the accumulated points can only be cashed out in Georgia.

CONCLUSION

Innovations implemented in banks simplify the use of banking products, make them more accessible and comfortable, all that in turn increases customer loyalty to a particular commercial bank. Loyalty programs are focused on long-term results in order to further increase the loyalty and trust of satisfied customers towards the bank.

To increase the number of loyal customers, the bank should constantly strive to offer products tailored to customers. The client is more loyal and devoted to the bank, the closer and more often he contacts it, this ensures a long-term relationship between the bank and the customer.

In order to make a profit, the business sector must take care of its customers, offer a product or service that meets their needs, otherwise, customers will not use its services. In order to attract and retain customers, a commercial bank offers them desirable tariffs and affordable interest rates, but the bank cannot gain a competitive advantage with this offer alone.

In addition to receiving short-term financial benefits, commercial banks must also see the importance of long-term qualitative benefits, which is reflected in customer satisfaction. In order to receive long-term benefits, the bank makes monetary investments and introduces loyalty programs. The introduction of loyalty programs does not bring quick results and the results appear only after a few years, because the population needs time to understand the novelty, and this time increases even more when it discusses the inclusion in this program. For a commercial bank, long-term benefits are more important than short-term benefits.

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